

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ТЕОРИИ ОРБИТ И УНИВЕРСАЛЬНОГО СУЩЕСТВОВАНИЯ

Гараев С.Г.

*к.б.н., ведущий научный сотрудник Института ботаники Министерства Науки и Образования,
Баку, Азербайджан*

"ORBITS" AND THEORIES OF UNIVERSAL EXISTENCE

Qarayev S.

*Ph.D. in Biology, Leading Researcher of the Institute of Botany,
Ministry of Science and Education Baku, Azerbaijan*

Аннотация

В теориях орбит и универсального существования выдвигаются и обосновываются новые идеи, отличающиеся от традиционных взглядов о возникновении Вселенной и материи. На основе данных теорий стоит первичность орбит, особенность синтезирования материи, набирая высокоскоростной энергии. Т.е. земля, юпитер и т.д. не создавали «орбиту», совершая траекторию вокруг солнца после своего возникновения. Наборот, сначала существовали орбиты, набирая световые фотоны $h\nu$, высокоскоростной энергии, создали землю, юпитер и т.д. А также, в данных теориях объяснение сложных связей между существованием и энергией действительности, причинно-следственных механизмов, дается в новом представлении. Выдвигается система различных взглядов о времени, пространстве, скорости, площадих. Теории орбит и универсального существования составляют единство и дополняют друг друга.

Abstract

Unlike traditional view about the origin of the universe and the matter there are putting forward and substantiated new ideas in **Orbits and universal existence theories**. Features such as orbits being first, collecting high-speed energy to synthesize matter are based on the basis of this theory. It means that, earth, Jupiter and others did not create "orbits" with trajectory around the sun. Instead, orbits existed before and by collecting high-speed energy and $h\nu$ photon of light formed earth, Jupiter etc. As well, explanation of complex relationship, cause and effect mechanisms between presence energy and existence is given in a new level. Different views system about time, location, speed, space is put forward. **Orbits and universal existence theories** is in unity and complement each other.

Ключевые слова: Приблизительная логика, реальная логика, синтез на орбитах, коэффициент существования, энергия действительности, время существования, Биг банг, бозон Хиггса, порции $h\nu$ -квантов, ограниченные и неограниченные поля.

Keywords- Estimated logic, real logic, synthesis in orbits, presence coefficient, presence energy, presence time, Bing bang, Higgs boson, $h\nu$ -quantum portions, limited and non-limited areas.

Introduction

Currently, accepted views.

Let's look through the logic and essence of "**Bing-Bang**" theory which currently is the most popular and accepted by the scientific community. Russian scientist Alexander Fredman and Belgian astrophysicist George Lemaytr theoretically calculated expansion of the universe. Then Hubbi determined that stars move away not only from us, at the same time moving away from each other. So the universe is expanding as time passes. In this case the density getting thinner and cold. Considering with this logic that time is going back, matter and energy settled at extremely density and very small point. Universe was originated by its explosion. [12, 13, 14, 15, 17].

They give arguments to prove the "Bing-Bang" theory. In "**Zariyat**" Sura's (51) 47th verse of The Holy Quran was said, "**We have created heaven with our power and are expanding it.**" [1]

According to George Gamov, if the universe originated from one point, after that explosion radiation

should be remained and equally distributed to all cosmos [8]. Robert Wilson and Arno Penziyas discovered waves containing these remains in 1965. George Smith and working with him NASA group sent into space artificial satellite named COBE in 1989. Due to the sensitive radars in satellite, approval of Penziya's and Wilson's calculations took eight minutes. [6,7]

Materials and methods

Supporters of "Bing-Bang" theory claim that, "**Big explosion**" take 10^{-43} seconds. Then begins **Plank era**. Meanwhile, the size of the universe has been up to 10^{35} meters-plank length. It occurs in 10^{-37} seconds. Then forms nucleus of the hydrogen atom. After nine billion years were formed the solar system. 13.7 billion years later universe is in current condition.. [11, 16]

Einstein also studied continuous expansion of the universe. However, it was contrary to the adopted static theory at that time, great scientist put aside his discovery. [9]

Detection of the Higgs boson could help to find answers to questions related with origin of mass, beginning of universe.

In October 8, 2013, Peter Higgs and Belgium physicist Francois Englert have received a Nobel Prize for research in this field. [4, 18, 19, 20]

Discussion and Conclusions

The approximateness of Bing Bang theory , "Higgs boson" , hypothesis of "smallest particles of God" and nuances which cannot be explained.

"Big-Bang"- approximateness, unexplained moments

1.The contrast with the Koran's logic

Bing Bang theory does not consistent with the logic of the **Koran**. There are more than twenty verse about the creation of heaven and earth in Koran **6/101., 7/54., 13/2., 21/30., 41/9,10,11,12., 44/10., 50/38., 79/27,29.[1]** As we see, there is no point, talking about the big explosion. Only noted that universe created from nothing, with truth and wisdom and this process lasted six days. In Bing Bang theory is spoken about a billion years. There is discrepancy of time and space.

We thought that, we must pay special attention to definition of TIME concept in the theory of the creation of the universe. Here is a complex issue which needs explanation. In Koran:**God controls the whole things from heaven to earth. "Then (the same works),which you count (the year) which is equal to a thousand year (the Day of Judgment) rises toward him (God)".** Bow Surah (32), verse 5. ; **" The angels and the Spirit will ascend to Him (as comparing with the world) during a Day the extent of which is fifty thousand years "** Maarij surah (70),verse 4.; **A day with your Lord is like a thousand years of those which you count.** Hajj surah (22),verse 47.[1]

Form of universe, space and time.

Vertically straight-line from the ground to top, from certain-point, approximate endpoint of logic, in scope of external logic, more precisely, will begin to bend to real logic after close range. If we enlarge circle to close distance to real logic , it will be get straight line form. **The Universe is in the form of circle crossing to straight line and straight line crossing to circle.** Everything in universe is inclined to take a form of globe. Globe is an ideal form of all existing. Other forms beside globe is radical forms. Globe is neutral and stable form. The ideal form of time is a straight line. The universe formed from unity of universe and space , and so form of universe is in periodic and dynamic form of circle transition to straight line and straight line crossing to circle.

Limited and unlimited space, time, speed. The essence of black holes.

All forms of motion, which is known to us is tranquil. That is with portions. Accordingly, known time form is with portions. Electrical, magnetic, gravitational fields is also in the portions, and **tranquil**. If this assumptions is true, then there are existing **absolute stillness moments of time** and on this moments time stops. According to this **time is with portions** too. At the same time, everything which is on the move, for example, Earth rotating in its orbit and other celestial bodies have moment of stillness, zero point. However, there is also forms of time and motion which have not moment of stillness, zero point. Finding **uninterrupted**, without points of **stillness forms** of time and

motion, can be determined speed faster than the speed of light. The **speed of light is tranquil** and has points of stillness. Speed of motion which is **tranquil** and has points of stillness is limited. The speed exceeding speed of light is unlimited speed. **Complete, entire areas can create unlimited speed, but not interrupted.** At the same time, only a complete, intact, non-limited areas can produce mass. Tranquil areas can't form mass. **Non-limited areas**, unlike electrical, magnetic, nuclear and gravitational forces, have **unlimited influence** and power. There are such unlimited mass and power in **black holes** created by unlimited, whole areas that, due to them, there is a reasonable environment energy, time and space form proper to external logic. Disappearance of attracted, not returning, not leaving a trace is unlimited energy, unlimited changing at the result of falling time and space environment. **Black holes themselves, can't be formed from extinct stars.** Because the stars have limited weight, power, strength, speed and other parameters. **Black holes are special orbits that, there is continuity and non limitation in its nature.** Only in this case, quantum of light which have tranquil, with limited speed and energy can disappear there.

When mentioned unlimited speed, time, energy, area it does not mean infinity of measure, but considered continuity, integrity.

Approximateness, other dark moments in theories about the origins of the universe.

The nature and origin of the point is unknown.

In "Bing Bang" theory are mentioned about zero time, space and energy. Then was said that there was only a small point. These ideas are opposite to each other. At the same time we noted that, **space and time can't be zero in absolute terms.** From zero, from nothing – nothing can be created.

There are two major evidence of "Bing Bang" theory : The expansion of the universe and the cosmic background radiation - the remnant after explosion, the waste. Let's look through at the second argument: They proved that there was formed cosmic background radiation at the result of "big explosion", the universe remains are keeping existence during billion years. They come to this logical conclusion because energy is not lost. So coming up with this logic, small point energy, mass and other parameters which is material of "big bang", must be equal to current universe. Point which considered smaller than Planck length, from where and how can collect such strength, energy? How that point has exploded? **The creation of the universe from point with unknown origin, physical, chemical, mathematical essence** is a product of approximate logic.

Periodicity in the Universe. Impossibility of constant expansion.

The logic of this idea is approximate too. The fact is that processes in the universe is **periodical**. In other words, the universe can be expanded at a certain time, or can be assembled. But in absolute terms can't be continuously and rapidly expanded. It is impossible. First of all, in this case the system would be lost its balance, could be collapsed. Stars, galaxies in universe make oscillation in the result of influence of gravitational and

other forces. This oscillation is round. Stars and galaxies does not move straight in their own orbits, but in **zigzags dance** in a small amplitude. The form of the universe, is not in a form of circle which we conceive with approximate logic, but close distance to real logic is in a form dynamic nature and periodic shape where straight line becomes circle and circle becomes straight line. **Permanently digression** is out of the question.

Here is a very simple truth. If the universe continually increasing, in this case it must be expanded wholly. That is all the components of the universe must be expanded compared to each other. In particular, the solar system must be expanded too. Earth from the sun, the moon and other planets and satellites must move away from the sun and from each other. However, this does not happen in reality. Otherwise, orbits of planets will lose their essence, in this case consequences would be definitely felt. At the same time, the universe is steadily increasing, which pushed it to expand, energy, power causing this process, had to expand diameter of stars, atoms and molecules.

As we know, none of these events do not happen in reality. In other words, **expansion of the universe is not constant and one lined**. One of the complex and combined form of action of stars and galaxies. Finally, if we accept that the universe is expanding steadily, we will come to the illogical conclusion. Expanding, fleeing from the centre forces are not creative but destructive, their influence could never have created the universe.

If planets will arise at the result of separation from the sun, they will be threaded according to increased or descending sequence of their mass. Venus would not be revolve on the other direction unlike other planets.[5]

To eliminate all these dark moments, approximateness, we put forward "Orbits" and "universal existence" theory which is closely related to each other.

The theory of orbits:

Planets generated by the accumulation the solar energy over the **orbits** and transformation to mass. If the energy collects with the speed of light there will be generate mass. The light ray cannot pass complete the lines orbits of planets. Orbits play the role of "Net" which hold and keep light rays, $h\nu$ -light portion ,electromagnetic waves. In the result accumulated energy turns into the mass. The structure of the atom was created from moving at the speed of light $h\nu$ portion of energy which are accumulated in orbits. Sun is formed from greater light, the source of light. Universe is formed as chain in this way. **Therefore the beginning of the universe is not a small point otherwise it has been the huge source of light**. Complex parameters of that source is equal to current universe or bigger than it.

The object is a pile of energy and energy is a pile of object. If the substance collapse in an instant it will turn into energy; if the energy collects in an instant turn to the substance. **Therefore the substance is formed from the instant collecting energy.** [2]

Orbits are collecting energy and convert them into matter. Different elements of object planets are created depending on essence of energy pile, time and space speed of summation. Inter-limited slaughtered areas

create unlimited areas in high speed. **Non uninterrupted limited areas create mass and unlimited mass**. Electromagnet area is interrupted. Concentration and accumulation are forming by stopping high speed interrupt areas. Process is caused creation of unlimited, full, uninterrupted areas. **Non limited, uninterrupted area has got uninterrupted energy. This energy accumulation means mass. So mass has uninterrupted, unlimited energy and unlimited energy has mass**. When we say unlimited is considered continuous whole field of energy

In short, **full and unlimited area are forming by the collection and compression of limited area with high speed that it gives mass to the elementary particles. Mass is a existence form of mutual relation over time concentrated, persistent areas. Concentrated area getting a particular essence**. Electron forms few and far between areas and that is why has not a mass.

When speedy and interrupted areas stopped and gathered instantly it turns to unlimited area, mass. **So orbits are first. There is a synthesis of substance**. Process is essentially compression and gathering. This is different process than short term higgs particles which forms in the result of speedy protons collision.

When the light and halo achieved to the certain measure and energy orbits appear around it. This measure is "**crisis**" **energy of source**. So after light source pass crisis measure and energy, around it forming orbits. The theory of orbits can be given in three postulate:

- The energy of Sun or "crisis" have orbits which has a have the potential to stationary levels around other past stars. There are **orbits- stationary levels** with special electromagnetic area, stable time and space measure, potential of intensify and accelerate which are formed around of the sun or crisis" energy passed other stars.

- Orbits holding the sun (light source) - $h\nu$ energy portions as "net" , it intensifies turning into full, unlimited persistent area and synthesised protons, neutrons, electrons, mass and substance.

- Orbits have properties to transfer system of relations among themselves with the sun (orbits around the sun, orbits of the planets) to the smallest particle which formed matter (the-nuclear-orbits-electrons inside atomic)

The beginning of the creation of the universe energy is a divine halo ,light. The stars and the sun is created as a result of synthesise of hole and light in orbits. **So, the orbits are the first , stars and planets are reproduction**. Each orbit according its essence formed stars or planets-Mercury, Mars, Venus, Earth and others. So **orbits was not created later, it exists before matter**.

The environment between stars are affected from relation between them, processes which is going inside orbits and celestial substances. Existence is following: God, God's wish, and the word "**Be!**", divine power, the energy of general universe, the divine halo. The energy of general universe, divine halo created onset orbits. The orbits formed stars and stars formed its own

orbits. **The synthesis of the universe in orbits has gone in the form of chain[2,3,8].**

Universal Availability Theory:

Each existing has its certain energy. It does not only belong to alive and inanimate. It belongs to the past present and future object and events, processes physical, chemical, mathematical, biological laws, created and creative's, in general belongs to everything.

Let's call it "**energy of being**". The question arises: Does energy of being appeared before or those who have? Are the object, event, law, created the first or energy of being belong those? Is energy of being is creative or reproduction? The creator which have caused of the result –must be the first existence energy.

Let's try to postulate a theory of **universal availability**:

- What exists in the universe, it is inside the circle of **energy of being general universe**. Circle means that the universe is not infinite. The universe is a form of open dynamic shape which the straight line transit to circle, and circle transit the straight line. This transitional form is infinite. Time is available for it. **The end of the universe is within real logic and ends with the right zero. Time is available before space.** Because the energy of being has been before availability. But time has formed inside of energy of being general universe. Certainly it is about the time of universe. The time of external logic is different. **In the sight of GOD time and space is complete.** It means that God can see Adam and Havva with us.

- The being energy of existence have been a part of being energy of universe ,created from it and located in its flatness. It is special (the length of wave and etc its parameters is unique), has the same time and lifetime with energy of general universe. The existence energy is in a globe form. So each existing is special. Evolution does not mean turning the existing ones to each others and the formation of birds from the reptiles. Each existing evolves lifetime, is developing from the primitive to higher. But on its own line. So, the bird has developed and stayed as a bird, does not become mammal. Oak has developed and remained as an oak, does not become plane. Everything that exists is doomed evolves lifetime, **reached to the peak point.** Because general evolution makes inevitable it.

- Everything for existing, needs being of energy of "mother's womb". 'Mother womb's ' of planets are orbits. ('Mother womb's 'of great works, geniuses' brains, the majority of battle contrasts in mankind and it deepness and etc.). But live, dead, events, discoveries, and great works – the being energy of all existing is flatness of being energy of universe, is an element of it and it has been before.

- True zero of being energy - is smaller than small structure unit the **quantum portion** (hv), forms it. True zero - being time of available was smaller than plank time and forms it.

- True zero of the energy of being ,the essence of being and available time and the essence of being energy of general universe of time is production of God's word" be" and a reflection of the power.To create is appearance and result (cause) of its order. Beginning of universe begins with wish, order of God's word-

"Be". **Order of "Be" is beginning, of light, halo, cause.**

- Being energies turning to time existence, were formed from existence of universe energy till day of Judgement with " **The necessity of evolutionary chain**" principle. The chain of importance evolution , is sequence of energy of being from primitive to high with the principle

- A part of everything that exists in the being energy creates area around it. **There is a production of existing area is in around of each existence. This area is affected other existing as well as human and it feels with different signals:** For example; Presence of the accident, felt by the people who is far from , you feel that ,you will see someone soon, and it means that ,the existence of that person comes up to you [3,10].

Universal Law of Existence

The being of energy and its essence is directly proportional to existence in real, and inertial proportional to the square of time (life).

$$V \approx Q \frac{EM}{T^2}$$

Approximations shows that all the energy of being dont turned to existence. Some part of it is spent the creation of special area around existence.

V- Real existence

Q- Existence coefficients

E- Existence energy

M- essence

T- time,existence life

E- Existence energy is invariable (since Day of Judgment) energy of existence that, it has in existing time before and after it. It is invariable, it is before the existence, and production of it. It is invariable and special for each existence. It means that, nothing disappeared without trace. For example: It thunders, its sound, light, energy does not disappeared, stayed in some form in universe.

Q- existence factor is the ratio of the smallest life of each existence to the smallest life.

It expressed being real essence ratio (after non-existence, before existence, transition form non-existence to existence) to the real zero life (smallest time interval from existence). Each existence has its existence factor.

T-The factor of existence and essence need time and thats why it is given to square. Being energy of the existence: $E = \frac{VT^2}{QM}$

$VT^2 = EQM$ - That is, multiplication of existence with its square of the life are equal to multiplication of existence coefficient to being energy and essence.

Some interesting assumptions:

- Those who feel the energy of existence in the past, are able to give information about some existing in the past and the future. For this, the third signal system must be develop in those humans.

- To find energy of existence has great importance in medicine (including cancer), and in the military.

- With blocking energy of existence, it is possible to make it invisible. Also, it is possible to make things invisible by sliding rays from the object.

- With transmission energy of existence, we can show one existence in different places at the same time.
 - Most likely, UFO due to the such broadcast, projections can pass through distance among universes (if there is any)[3,10].

It is impossible to find the source of the mass of matter by crashing elemental particles. **Mass are existence form of unlimited, uninterrupted area wave and particle (dualism) properties energies interaction with time.** Practical experiences should be carried out in the direction of collecting and compacting limited speed of light and restricted areas, to create continuous, non-restricted areas. And should be created a special atmosphere which will perform the function of orbits.

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